
Appraisal of Teachers' Perception of Motivational Activities and Its Influence on Their Job Performance: A Case Study of Lagos State Schools.

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Abstract

This study investigated "Appraisal of Teachers' Perception of Motivational Activities and Its Influence on Their Job Performance: A Case Study of Lagos State Schools." One research question guided the study. Literature review was carried out in areas pertinent to the study. The design of the study was a descriptive survey. Out of a population of 3,114 senior secondary school teachers, 612 of them drawn by simple random and stratified random sampling techniques constituted the sample of the study. Data for the study were collected using a questionnaire titled "Motivational Incentives and Teachers' Job Performance (MITJP)". The instrument was developed and validated by the researcher while the reliability of the instrument was determined by test-retest and Pearson product-moment correlation technique, with a reliability coefficient of 0.80. The result of the data was analyzed using percentages. Results of the study indicated that the motivational items surrounding monetary incentives, welfare activities, and provision and availability of adequate instructional materials are all strong motivational factors that influence teachers' job performance. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that the Post Primary Schools Services, Lagos State, under whose auspices the motivation of secondary school teachers lies should ensure that teachers' salaries and entitlements are promptly paid; seminars, workshops and conferences are organized regularly to keep abreast of innovative skills; promotions are given to teachers as and when due and that welfare facilities like provision of staff bus and staff quarters as well as access to mortgage and car loans are considered.

Keywords: Teachers' Perception, Motivational Activities, Job Performance, Lagos State Schools

1.0 Introduction

Governments and organizations may build and equip schools with basic science and technical equipment, provide all the basic educational materials, renovate and rehabilitate all old schools, provide libraries and other necessary facilities as well as employ the best qualified staff, yet the problem confronting educational administration would be half solved if the teachers who are the bedrock of education are not motivated.

The education sector in Nigeria and across the globe has undergone a profound and transformative shift in recent times. Governments, curriculum planners, parents, and the students themselves are concerned with the quality-of-service delivery from our teachers. Education has the purpose of catalyzing the transformation of society for its development. Education has the potential to equip people with the skills, attitudes, and norms needed to hold governments to account, to challenge autocracy, and to assess policies that affect their lives (Glaeser et al., 2009). At an individual level, education is a crucial determinant of whether people have the capabilities, literacy, confidence, and attitudes that they need to participate in society. As a concrete example, when poor and marginalized people are educated, they are often more likely to participate in meetings of local political bodies and devolved bodies managing education, health, and water resources (Alsop & Kurey, 2005). Education transcends the mere acquisition of knowledge and skills; hence the development of an individual who is transformed with the ability to understand and manipulate this world (Otunga, Odeo & Barasa, 2011).

The success and failure in achieving quality education lie primarily with teachers. Teachers play a vital role in ensuring high-quality education. Nyakundi (2012) explains that teacher motivation is the most important factor in the promotion of teaching and learning excellence. He further adds, motivated teachers are more likely to motivate students to learn and to ensure the implementation of education reform. Therefore, the quality of an educational system cannot outperform the quality of its teachers (Federal Ministry of Education FME, 2007).

A survey conducted recently on teachers' motivation and job satisfaction in 12 countries in Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria, raises concerns about the low motivation among the teachers, which has led to teacher absenteeism, lateness, and lack of commitment to their work (Bennell and Akyeampong, 2007). Other studies have investigated variables of motivation such as working environment, management leadership style, incentives to employees, and participation in decision-making.

Workers in any organization need something to keep them working. Most of the time, the salaries of the employees are not enough to encourage and motivate them to work. An employee must be motivated to enhance productivity.

Motivation, therefore, is not bribery or manipulation; it is understanding the needs of workers and providing ways to help them attain or satisfy those needs by the organization. Individual differences, choices, and preferences exist, and this implies that what motivates a person may or may not motivate another to the same degree. A person may find monetary rewards and allowances highly motivating, while another person derives a strong drive from professional development and training. Not all employees share the same motivational drive; therefore, understanding each employee's needs and assisting them to reach their satisfied drivers is also a way of motivating them (Lipman, 2014).

Teacher motivation is an essential component to enhance classroom effectiveness (Carson & Chase, 2009). As students' learning outcomes are highly dependent on the quality of instruction, teaching effectiveness has been explored in terms of teaching styles, teacher

approach, teaching practice, and instruction behaviours in relation to teacher motivation factors (Butler & Shibaz, 2014).

Several researchers, for the purpose of their studies, have developed a working definition for teacher motivation and job satisfaction. According to Gulnaz, Ahmad, and Mandouh (2015), the word “motivation” can be defined as the intrinsic and extrinsic drives or forces that determine focus and direct the behaviour of the learners towards a specific target or goal. Intrinsic motivation comes from one’s self-desire to seek out new things, to challenge oneself, the eagerness to learn, to gain knowledge, and to explore self-values and capabilities. When a person has intrinsic motivation, it means he or she does the job with interest and enjoyment. Some factors create extrinsic motivation, for example, competitions, appraisals, external rewards, or punishment. (Dewani 2013). (Manzoor, 2012). Sharif and Nazir (2016) ascertained that different components and factors affect employees’ job satisfaction. They further opined that a sound working environment, pay and promotion, job security, and level of fairness share a significant relationship with job satisfaction. When an employee is motivated, he or she shows enthusiasm and eagerness towards the work and a strong determination to implement and accomplish the work tasks (Moran, 2013).

Job performance is defined as the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioral episodes that an individual carries out over a standard period. Performance refers only to behaviors that can make a difference to organizational goal accomplishment. Employee motivation has a strong influence on the effectiveness of an organization. (Paul, 2017).

The need for this study arose out of the researcher's concern for the need to redress the sagging morale of teachers resulting from inadequate attention paid to their welfare (Richardson, 2014). Nbina (2012) opined that teachers of today are buffered by many challenges that dampen their morale and lower their motivation to perform effectively, and this could harm the educational system.

Research Question

This study then tends to ask the following question:

What are the motivational activities that can influence teachers’ job performance?

2.0 Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

The Concept of Motivation

The concept of motivation in the context of this study has been treated by different writers and researchers. Teacher motivation is an important field of research, especially in a country like Nigeria, where teacher quality has become a prominent concern.

Motivation is a goal-directed behaviour. Motivated employees exert more effort to perform a given task than those who are less motivated. Intrinsic factors are generally described in terms of a desire to work with children and contribute to society (Chong & Low, 2009). Furthermore, studies have suggested teacher motivation is related to professional commitment, efficacy, organizational citizenship, and participation in professional development (Morgan, Kitching, & O’Leary, 2007).

High-quality education is emphasized as the key tool for the development of young citizens with the competences they need to adapt to a globalized society. Teachers play a vital role in ensuring high-quality education. Nyakundi (2012) explained that teacher motivation is the most important factor in the promotion of teaching and learning excellence. He further adds

that motivated teachers are more likely to motivate students to learn and to ensure the implementation of education reform. Therefore, the quality of an educational system cannot outperform the quality of its teachers.

Gredler et al. (2004) broadly define motivation as “the attribute that moves us to do or not to do something”. Broussard and Garrison (2004) observe that contemporary motivation research tends to be organized around three questions: a) Can I do this task? b) Do I want to do this task and why? c) What do I have to do to succeed in this task? It is the level of motivation one has that drives the response or answer to be given to those questions observed by Broussard and Garrison (2004).

Guajardo (2011) describes motivation as the willingness, drive, or desire to engage in good teaching. According to Gulnaz et al. (2015), the word “motivation” can be defined as the intrinsic and extrinsic drives or forces that determine focus and direct the behaviour of the learners towards a specific target or goal.

In the absence of motivation, it is demotivation. Ushioda (2011) also suggested five categories of demotivating factors, including stress, inhibition of teacher autonomy, insufficient self-efficacy, inadequate career structures, content repetitiveness, and limited potential for intellectual development.

A careful examination of the foregoing definitions and explanations of motivation leads to some conclusions:

- i. Involves purposive, designated, and goal-directed behavior.
- ii. Deals with what starts and energizes human behaviour, how it is directed, and sustained.
- iii. Is related not only to behaviour but also to performance,
- iv. Involves certain forces acting on or within a person to initiate and direct behaviour,
- v. Is not directly measured but inferred from behaviour.

Concept of Job Performance

Job performance refers to as the total expected value to the organization of the discrete behavioral episodes that an individual carries out over a standard period. Viswesvaran and Ones (2000) defined job performance as behaviour and outcomes that employees undertake that contribute to organizational goals. Job performance is related to the extent to which an employee can accomplish the task assigned to him or her and how the accomplished task contributes to the realization of the organizational goal (Mawoli & Babandako, 2011).

Theoretical framework

The Theory of Motivation

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Theory (Maslow, 1954)

This has been a very popular motivation theory and can be applied in every organization. He saw human needs in the form of a hierarchy, ascending from the lowest to the highest, and he concluded that when one set of needs is satisfied, this kind of need ceases to be motivation. He therefore placed the basic human needs in an ascending order of importance as follows:

- i. **Physical Needs:** These are basic needs for sustaining human life itself, such as physical comfort, pay, and basic working conditions. He pointed out that until these needs are satisfied to the degree necessary to maintain life, other needs will not motivate people. In the workplace such as the school, the salaries paid to workers help them to fulfill this category of needs.
- ii. **Safety Needs:** When the physiological needs are successfully satisfied, safety needs become the dominant force in the personality of the individual. Safety needs are

mainly concerned with maintaining order and security. People feel the need of structure, law and order and to be under someone's direction.

- iii. **Social Needs:** This is in the form of friendliness with colleagues, belongings, and association for love. This need is dependent on the fulfillment of previous categories of needs. It is concerned with making intimate relationships with other members of society, being an accepted member of the organized group, and needing a family environment.
- iv. **Esteem Needs:** Esteem needs are divided into two categories: self-esteem, self-respect, self-regard, and self-evaluation on the one hand and those relating to respect from others, such as reputation, status, social success, and fame, on the other hand.
- v. **Self-Actualization:** This is the highest need in the hierarchy. It means to fulfill one's nature in all its aspects, being what one can be. People can be motivated towards self-actualization only when their lower-order needs have been met. From Maslow's point of view, a teacher without physical comfort, pay, and basic working conditions is not motivated and cannot be satisfied doing the work.

Empirical Studies on Teacher's Motivation and Its Influence on Their Job Performance

Some studies have been conducted by researchers on teachers' motivation and job performance among primary and secondary school teachers.

Duru (1992) studied the job performance among Nigerian teachers with special reference to Anambra State. Results of the study indicated, among others, that poor salary, lack of promotion, and poor conditions of service are responsible for teachers' poor performance in their job.

In a related study carried out by Ogbu (1981) titled "A study of the factors that influence teachers' job motivation" was conducted in Primary schools in Enugu State. Results of the study, among others, indicated that;

1. Regular payment of salaries and other allowances and promotion of teachers as when due, promote teachers' job motivation.
2. Provision of instructional materials and welfare services also enhance teachers' work motivation.

Shah et al. (2012) conducted a study on Job satisfaction and motivation of teachers of public education institutions in Nigeria. The study was conducted to determine the impact of reward and recognition, satisfaction with supervision, and work itself on job satisfaction. Moreover, the relationship between job satisfaction and work motivation was also explored with the help of responses collected from employees working in public educational institutions in the Rawalpindi area. The result showed a significant positive relationship between reward and recognition, satisfaction with supervision and the work itself, with job satisfaction, as well as a very significant positive relationship that was also observed between job satisfaction and intrinsic motivation.

Iliya and Ifeoma (2015) studied the Assessment of Teacher Motivation approaches in less developed countries. The study examined both traditional and new approaches to teacher motivation threats and measurement for shaping teacher motivation. The study result revealed that intrinsic rewards such as self-respect, responsibility, and a sense of accomplishment as well as participatory school improvement, comprehensive staff development and supportive teacher evaluation hold great promise for improving teachers' professional motivation.

3.0 Methodology

The design of the study is a descriptive survey. All the senior secondary school teachers in Education District V in Lagos State constituted the population of this study. The teachers were 3,114 in 2020 when this study was conducted. The district is made up of four education zones, namely: Ajeromi/Ifelodun, Amuwo Odofin, Badagry, and Ojo. Information obtained from Post Primary School Service Commission (PPSSC) Headquarters, Ikeja, revealed that out of the 139 senior secondary schools in the district, there are 39, 40, 28, and 32 in Ajeromi/Ifelodun, Amuwo Odofin, Badagry, and Ojo zones, respectively.

A combination of simple random sampling and stratified random sampling was used for this study. A total of 28 senior secondary schools (7 in each zone), selected through simple random sampling techniques, were used for the study. This means that the sample consisted of 20% of the teachers in each of the four zones in Education District V.

The sample of this study consisted of 612 senior secondary school teachers, drawn by stratified random sampling techniques. The stratification was in line with the teachers' gender, location, and level of experience. The gender consists of male and female. The location strata include urban and rural areas. The urban and rural areas were chosen in line with the Lagos State standard. The rural area by this standard is Badagry Local Government Area in Education district V, where the study was conducted, while the other three local government areas/zones, Ajeromi/Ifelodun, Amuwo Odofin, and Ojo, are classified as urban areas. Furthermore, experienced teachers referred to teachers who have spent 3 years and above on the job while teachers who have spent below 3 years are said to be 'new on the job'.

Details of the stratified sample population in percentage are as follows: Male teachers: 42%, Female teachers: 58%, Experienced teachers: 68%, Inexperienced teachers: 32%, Urban area teachers: 68%, Rural area teachers: 32%.

Data for the study was collected using a questionnaire titled "Motivational Incentives and Teachers' Job Performance (MITJP)" (This is found in Appendix A).

An initial pool of 30 items (15 items in section A and 15 items in section B) that constituted draft of the instruments were sent to two specialists in Educational Measurement and Administration and two secondary school teachers to vet the instrument in terms of the clarity of words and suitability of the listed items in enhancing the senior secondary school teachers' job performance. The reliability coefficient of the instrument (MITJP) was determined using the test-retest method using 10 teachers. The scores were correlated using the Pearson product-moment correlation technique. A reliability coefficient of 0.80 was obtained for the instrument. The value was considered high enough and thus adequate for the study. The computation is shown in Appendix B. Although 623 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, only 612, representing 98%, were returned and used in data analysis.

4.0 Discussion of findings

Research Question: What are the motivational activities that can influence teachers' performance?

Table 1: Motivational Activities

S/N	Items	YES	NO
1.	Prompt payment and periodic increments of salaries.	90%	10%
2.	Teachers' promotion as at when due.	85%	15%
3.	Teachers' professional autonomy and authority.	85%	15%
4.	Provision of staff bus.	70%	30%
5.	Reward/recognition of excellent performers	95%	5%
6.	Provision of conducive staff quarters.	90%	10%
7.	Granting access to mortgage and car loans.	85%	15%
8.	Prompt payment of gratuities and pensions.	95%	5%
9.	Provision of relevant textbooks, journals, magazines and instructional materials.	85%	15%
10	Provision conducive classroom and school environment.	90%	10%
	Average	87%	13%

Table 1 above reveals that the items listed are perceived by the teachers as strong motivational factors that are considered capable of enhancing their job performance.

95% of the respondents agreed that reward/recognition of excellent performers and prompt payment of gratuities and pensions strongly motivates them, while 90% of them revealed that prompt payment and periodic increment of salaries, provision of conducive staff quarters, and provision conducive classroom and school environment are their strong motivators.

The results of the findings in Table 1 above furthermore expose that 85% of the respondents find teachers' promotion as at due highly motivating, as well as teachers' professional autonomy and authority, granting access to mortgage and car loans, provision of relevant textbooks, journals, magazines, and instructional materials.

However, the provision of a staff bus was found less motivating, as only 70% of the respondents agreed to its usefulness.

5.0 Conclusion

The result of this study shows a strong acceptance of the listed motivational items as strongly motivating, with the evidence of a total of 87% of the respondents' acceptance that the motivational items strongly motivate them and enhance their job performance. The motivational items surrounding monetary incentives, welfare activities, and provision and availability of adequate instructional materials are all strong motivational factors that influence teachers' job performance.

This result supports the position of Duru (1992), who studied the job performance among Nigerian teachers and revealed that poor salary, lack of promotion, and poor conditions of service are responsible for demotivated teachers and negatively influence their performance on their job. Abba (2014) also revealed that employees with high motivation are thought to have better work performance and overall resulting in better, more productive, and effective company performance. The findings of this study also reveal that the impact of motivational incentives on teachers and employees of any organization cannot be overemphasized. Organizations across the globe that consider their human resources as a central core of the

business and continuously increase the level of their employees' motivation and performance tend to be more effective (Adi, 2000; Anka 1988; Robthberg 2005).

6.0 Recommendations

Based on the findings of this work, the following recommendations were made. The Post Primary Schools Services, Lagos State, under whose auspices the motivation of secondary school teachers lies, should ensure that:

- Teachers' salaries are promptly paid.
- Seminars, workshops, conferences, and symposia are organized regularly for teachers to keep abreast with innovative skills/strategies in their subject areas.
- Promotions are given to teachers as due. Welfare facilities are adequately provided to teachers, such as access to mortgage loans, car loans, provision of a staff bus, and staff quarters.
- All teachers' entitlements and allowances are given to them as due. Adequate arrangements are made for the payment of gratuities, pensions, and other entitlements to retired and retiring teachers.
- Infrastructural and instructional facilities are adequately provided for the effective discharge of the teachers' duties.
- Incentives are given to teachers without favoritism of any sort.
- There is no outright denial of teachers' rights and incentives or bonuses earned or deserved.

REFERENCES

- Bennell, P., & Akyeampong, K. (2007). Teacher motivation in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia. *Department for International Development, [DFID]: Educational Papers, 1*(1), 8-20.
- Broussard, S. C., & Garrison, M. E. B. (2004). The relationship between classroom motivation and academic achievement in elementary school-aged children. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal, 33*(7), 106-120.
- Butler, R. & Shibaz, L. (2014). Striving to connect and striving to learn: Influences of relational and mastery goals for teaching on teacher behaviors and student interest and help seeking. *International Journal of Educational Research, 65*(10), 10-16.
- Carson, Russell L.; Chase, Melissa A. (2009). An examination of physical education teacher motivation from a self-determination: A theoretical framework. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy, 14*(24), 335-353.
- Chong, S., & Low, L. (2009). Why I want to teach and how I feel about teaching – formation of teacher identity from pre-service to the beginning teacher phase. *Educational Research Policy and Practice, 8*(16), 59-72.
- Dewani, V. (2013). *Motivation*. Retrieved from <https://www.slideshare.net/vijaydewani7/motiva>
- Duru, A.O. (1992). Level of job performance among Nigerian teachers. *The Administrator, 2*(2), 8 - 5.
- Federal Ministry of Education, [FME], Nigeria. (2007). *Education reform act.: Arrangement of parts (Education sector reform bill)*. Abuja, Nigeria: Author.
- Glaeser, E.L., Matt, R., & Kristina, T. (2009). Inequality in cities. *Journal of Regional Science, 49*(4), 23-62.
- Gredler, M.E., Broussard, S.C. & Garrison, M.E.B. (2004). The relationship between classroom motivation and academic achievement in elementary school and aged children. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal, 3*(3), 106-120.
- Guajardo, J. (2011). Teacher motivation: Theoretical framework, situation analysis of save the children country offices and recommended strategies. *Save the Children Basic Education Reform, 12*(14), 214-242.
- Gulnaz, F., Ahmad, A. and Mandouh, S.A. (2015). An exploration of the demotivational factors affecting teaching and learning of English as foreign language (EFL) in gulf countries. *International Journal of Social Sciences, 2*(1), 17-32.
- Iliya, A. and Ifeoma, L. G. (2015). Assessment of teacher motivation approaches in less developed countries. *Journal of Education and Practice, 6*(22), 10 – 17.
- Lipman, V. (2014). New study answers: What motivates employees to “go the extra miles?”. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/sites/victorlipman/2014/11/04/what-motivatesemployees-to-go-the-extra-mile-study-offers-surprising-answer/#77eeefa3a055>
- Manzoor, Q. A. (2012). Impact of employees’ motivation on organizational effectiveness. *European Journal of Business and Management, 3*(5), 25-52.
- Maslow, A.H. (1954). *Motivation and personality*. New York, NY: Harper & Row.
- Mawoli, M.A. and Babandako, A.Y. (2011). An evaluation of staff motivation, dissatisfaction and job performance in an academic setting. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research, 1*(5), 1-13.
- Moran, B. B. (2013). *Library and information center management*. California, CA: Libraries Unlimited.
- Morgan, M., Kitching, K. & O’Leary, M. (2007). The psychic rewards of teaching: Examining global, national and local influences on teacher motivation. *American*

- Educational Research Association*, 2(2), 19-28. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/234708395_The_Psychic_Rewards_of_Teaching_Examining_Global_National_and_Local_Influences_on_Teacher_Motivation
- Nbina, J.B. (2012). Teachers' competence and students' academic performance in senior secondary schools Chemistry: Is there any relationship? *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 11(1), 5-18.
- Nyakundi, T. K. (2012). *Factors affecting teacher motivation in pacific secondary schools in Thika west district, Kiambu country*. School of Education, Kenyatta University. Retrieved from <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Factors-Affecting-Teacher-Motivation-In-Nyakundi/563c0e7163f6fb105c6804f7581d954f4b8be336>
- Ogbu, D.C. (1981). Factors that influence teacher's job motivation. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 18 (2), 40-49.
- Otunga, R., Odero, I. & Barasa, P. (2011). A handbook for curriculum & instruction. *Moi University Inaugural Lecture Series*, 10(6), 225-252.
- Paul, E. (2017). *10 ways to improve employee motivation*. Retrieved from <http://www.emptrust.com/blog/ways-to-improve-employee-motivation>
- Richardson, E. (2014). *Teacher motivation in low income contexts: An actionable framework for intervention, teacher motivation working group*. Retrieved from <http://www.teachersforefa.unesco.org/tmwg/blog2/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/Teacher-Motivation-in-Low-Income-Contexts.pdf> on 10.08.2016
- Sharif, U.F. and Nazir, A. (2016). An investigative study on job satisfaction level of employees working in software industry: A viewpoint of employees in Pakistan. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(1), 415-432.
- Viswesvaran, C.V. & Ones, D.S. (2000). Perspective on models of job performance. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 8(4), 216-226.

APPENDIX A
MOTIVATIONAL INCENTIVES AND TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE (MITJP)

Section A: Personal Data

Please provide the following information about you. A tick () may be used where necessary.

1. **Name of School**.....
2. **Gender:** Male () Female ()
3. **Work Experience:** Below 3 years(); 3 years and above().

Section B: Motivational Incentives to Teachers.

Kindly tick appropriately. Tick **YES** if you perceive them to be motivational incentives and **NO** if you do not.

S/N	Items	YES	NO
1.	Prompt payment and periodic increments of salaries.		
2.	Teachers' promotion as at when due.		
3.	Teachers' professional autonomy and authority.		
4.	Provision of staff bus.		
5.	Reward/recognition of excellent performers		
6.	Provision of conducive staff quarters.		
7.	Granting access to mortgage and car loans.		
8.	Prompt payment of gratuities and pensions.		
9.	Provision of relevant textbooks, journals, magazines and instructional materials.		
10.	Provide a conducive classroom and school environment.		

APPENDIX B

DETERMINATION OF THE RELIABILITY OF THE INSTRUMENT (MITJP) USING THE PEARSON MOMENT CORRELATION TECHNIQUE.

Formula:
$$R = \frac{N\sum XY - \sum X \sum Y}{\sqrt{(N\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2)(N\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2)}}$$

Where: R= Pearson product moment correlation coefficient.

XZY = Two sets of scores obtained from the same group of subjects during test.

Σ = sum of; N= Number of subjects.

S/N	X	Y	X'	Y ²	XY
1	57	55	3249	3025	3135
2	66	60	4356	3600	3960
3	60	52	3600	2704	3120
4	51	48	2601	2304	2448
5	80	72	6400	5184	5760
6	54	48	2916	2304	2592
7	63	54	3969	2916	3402
8	57	64	3249 -	4096	3648
9	60	50	3600	2500	3000
10	69	64	4761	4096	4416
Total	617	567	35452	32729	35481

Substituting in the above formula:

$$10 \times 103882 - 1748 \times 1739$$

$$(10 \times 104486) - (1748)^2 (10 \times 104665 - 1739)^2$$

$$76688 = 7668$$

$$(79076)(115829)$$